

SLEEP PROBLEM IN CHILDREN AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Melis AVCI, PhD

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Abstract

Sleep has a prominent place in the physical and psychological development of children. Mothers and fathers often look for a solution to this situation by expressing that their children do not want to sleep at a certain time, and sometimes even the whole household does not sleep. In this study, sleep problems in children and recommendations are discussed. Clinical Psychologists conduct the process of investigating, deciding the causes of problems and psychological support in such cases. In the article, amazingly effective methods to cope with the sleep problem in children are mentioned. The Function of Sleep: For centuries, the nature and function of sleep has been a subject of interest to humanity and science. Sleep and rest play a key role in keeping health and preventing diseases. Many researchers converge on the restorative effect of sleep, its homeostatic function, normal thermoregulation, and energy conservation effects. In delta sleep, heart rhythm slows down, respiratory rate decreases, body temperature decreases, metabolic activities slowdown in general, and body rest and regulation are provided. Thus, the energy use during sleep is minimized and arrangements are made in the vegetative system. Sleep reduces or relieves stress and anxiety. After a stressful day, an individual's active sleep increases.

Keywords: *Child, Problem, Sleep, Clinical Psychologist, Suggestion.*

1. Sleep Problem in Children

Sleep Physiology

Sleep and wakefulness are regulated by the reticular activating system (RAS) located in the brainstem, spinal cord, and cerebral cortex, and by the bulbar synchronized region (BSR) located in the medulla. RAS and BSR work together to control the natural cycle of sleep. Sleep is an active inhibition process. Brain centers are intermittently inhibited and activated, inhibition causes sleep and activation provides wakefulness. RAS provides the formation of reflex and voluntary movements as well as cortical activities associated with wakefulness, as well as detecting some stimuli coming from the periphery of the body and cerebral cortex during sleep, and in this case, the state of wakefulness is passed. Decreased stimuli reduce the activation of the system. External stimuli such as pain, noise, and pressure stimulate the reticular activating system, causing the body to switch from sleep to wakefulness. The increase in the activity of the bulbar synchronizer region initiates sleep. In other words, the decrease in the activity of the reticular activating system and the increase in the activation of the bulbar synchronizer region provide the transition from wakefulness to sleep time.

Many physical, psychological, and environmental factors negatively affect the quality of sleep. Many crucial factors such as the person's age, gender, diseases, medications, nutritional status, physical environment and psychological state affect sleep.

Sleep is a normal cyclical physiological state in which consciousness, wakefulness, and voluntary movements are lost. Visual, auditory, and tactile senses lost during sleep return in a brief time. There are two parts of sleep: 1- The active sleep period, which includes rapid eye movements and is defined as the REM (rapid eye movement) period, 2- Non-Rapid Eye Movement (NonREM) period. There are four stages of the NonREM period in adults, and sleep gets deeper as the stages progress. Each cycle takes about 90 minutes. Sleep periods in early childhood are not as well developed as in adults. Five different sleep and wakefulness stages are defined in infants: 1- Deep sleep period: Eyes are closed, breathing is regular, no movement. 2- Active sleep period: Eyes are closed, respiratory movements are irregular, small twitches may occur, although there is no obvious body movement. 3- Awake and silent period: Eyes are open, there is no obvious movement in the body, breathing is regular. 4- Active wakefulness period: Eyes are open; There are marked movements of the head, extremities, and trunk. Respiration is irregular. 5- Crying period: Eyes are slightly or completely closed.

While the sleep duration is 16-18 hours in total in a newborn baby; In a one-month-old baby, it decreases to an average of 14-16 hours. This sleep and wakefulness system is regulated by the development of the central nervous system. Studies have shown that the child is under the influence of intense stimuli during the active period of REM sleep; this has been shown to promote neurological development. Therefore, as the infant develops, REM sleep decreases, while the duration of nonREM sleep increases. However, every child has a unique sleep pattern. Some babies sleep all day, while others sleep for as little as nine hours. It is accepted that the sleep pattern is formed when the baby starts to sleep for 5-6 hours without interruption at night. With the formation of a cyclical sleep rhythm, daytime sleep shifts to nighttime periods. This can happen at various times for each baby.

The family should be told that the baby's developmental stages can affect the sleep pattern. For example, Unrest during the eruption of teeth, 4-5. After a month, it can disrupt the night's sleep. It is important to tell the parents that this situation is temporary and will improve. Breastfed babies

have been shown to wake up more frequently at night than formula-fed babies. Ambient temperature is also especially important. Especially in our society, there is a tendency to keep babies in warm environments and dress them too much. Babies who are put to bed in a warm environment with a lot of cover wake up more frequently at night than those who are laid down in a suitable temperature. 7-9. Anxiety due to separation from the mother, which is seen in infants in the last six months, is also an important condition that disrupts sleep patterns. This condition can also develop in babies of working mothers. The baby, who is separated from his mother and is restless during the day, perceives the sleep period as a second separation, and his sleep pattern is disturbed. The procedures applied to the baby during the sleep period by the parents or the caregiver should be questioned and reviewed by the doctor. It is important to ensure the close relationship of the baby with other caregivers in order to minimize the anxiety of separation from the mother. It can be recommended to parents because the baby's distraction or bath before going to bed (for example, by having a look at a picture book) has a calming effect. A favorite toy or dress can help the child sleep. A subdued nightlight can promote sleep. Such details give confidence to the child, and when he wakes up at night, they allow him to fall asleep again, even if the parents are not with him. In addition to these, the family should be told that it is very natural for the baby to cry during the process of establishing a sleep pattern.

In the formation of sleep-wake cycles, caregivers (mother or mother or child) by means of methods such as the regulation of naps during the day, the time to go to sleep, the development of pre-sleep rituals (behavior that has become a habit) or the use of tools that can help the child calm himself when he wakes up, for example, the use of dolls. another caregiver) helps the child. At the same time, the caregiver controls the sleep-disturbing stimuli in the environment and develops behaviors that support attachment and separation experiences. With the second and third age, sleep gains different meanings. For example, it is a time to calm down after an active day. Dealing with darkness and loneliness becomes necessary. The caregiver needs to adapt to boundaries and bedtime rituals. To be separated from the mother, the child must have developed a sufficiently secure attachment (Scher, 2001). There is an important relationship between problems in the mother-child relationship and sleep problems (Scher, 2001). In the seventh and ninth months, sleep problems are usually associated with excessive desire for stimuli for the balance system. In these months, children may need to be swayed and hugged for long periods in order to fall asleep. 10-12, when separation anxiety begins. Problems falling asleep reach the highest frequency. 13.-18. In these months, excessive activity during the day and exposure to excessive stimuli are more associated with sleep problems. 19.-24. While the problems experienced during falling asleep decrease from the first months, frequent awakenings can be seen at night.

Sleep disorders are problems that are very common in all age groups and can significantly impair the daily functionality, attention and learning skills of people at any age. On the other hand, memory problems, irritability, and increased sensory sensitivity can be seen. For many parents, sleep problems in their young children are quite distressing.

It is common to wake up crying at night between the ages of one and two, and to fall asleep between the ages of 2-3 (Goodlin-Jones et al., 2001; Burnham, 2002). Mostly, these problems are not objective findings, but complaints of parents. In babies with normal growth and development, these problems are often associated with temperament characteristics, attachment style, parental stress level, and maternal depression. In children with no normal development, it can often be associated with neurological and physical abnormalities (Wiggs and Stores, 1999).

Sleep habits may have different norms in different cultures. Especially in eastern societies, sleeping with a baby is a common behavior. This habit continues until puberty in some African countries. The habit of co-sleeping is also common in families with low socioeconomic status. Economic impossibilities, lack of adequate beds and rooms can also be an important reason for this behavior. While babies who sleep together in almost every culture wake up more frequently than babies who sleep in their own rooms, especially white families and families with higher socioeconomic status express that they are uncomfortable with these awakenings. Recording the sleep and wake times of babies by families who describe sleep problems provides objective data to understand the extent of the problem.

In parallel with physical, cognitive and social development and change in preschool ages, there are significant changes in sleep-wake cycles and sleep patterns. Providing a sleep pattern that is compatible with the child's individual characteristics and cultural expectations is very important for the health of the child and the family. Usually, when children reach the age of 5-6, they have a regular sleep rhythm and bed habit. At this age, it is necessary for the child to be given regular, consistent and patient sleep and bed training by the parents in order to gain the habit of sleeping without difficulty and being able to sleep alone. In this process, factors such as the temperament of the child, whether there is a conflict in the family, the general medical and psychiatric conditions of the parents and other family members are also factors.

The daily need for sleep in adolescence is 8-9 hours, which is higher than that of children and adults. Despite the increased need for sleep, the effect of factors specific to this period shortens the daily sleep duration and many problems may occur. ("Determination of Healthy Life Style Behaviours of the Students in ... - ed") Sleeping late at night and waking up late in the morning are the sleep characteristics of this period and have two important reasons; (a) Not getting enough sleep due to academic and increasing social activities, (b) Tendency to go to bed and wake up late with increasing age. In addition, respiratory system diseases (such as septum deviation and adenoid vegetation), which are quite common in children and adolescents, increase the incidence of sleep disorders. In recent years, the increase in obesity rates in this age group; It brings about an increase in the rate of obstructive sleep apnea and related sleep problems. Although 10-28% of adolescents have sleep problems such as waking up frequently at night, refusing to wake up, and sleeping excessively during the day, they are rarely recognized and treated. There may also be sleep problems in the form of hypersomnia (excessive prolongation of sleep at night) or increased daytime sleepiness and insomnia (difficulty falling or staying asleep).

Psychosocial sleep disorders include:

1. *Problems with bed and sleeping place: While preparing for sleep, the child may show resistance and experience anger attacks. Usually, he may be stubborn about sleeping in places that his parents do not approve (in the living room, in the parents' bed, etc.). Families cannot resist the child's resistance after a while, and the child gains the habit of not sleeping in his own bed.*
2. *Difficulty falling asleep and frequent awakenings: The child is not accustomed to falling asleep without the facilitation of his parents. He often wants to wake up and feel the closeness and reassurance of his parents.*
3. *Fears associated with sleep and bedtime: Fear and anxiety, such as fear of the dark, fear of burglars, and fear of not being alone, can negatively affect the child's sleep pattern.*

Biological and developmental sleep disorders include:

1. *Parasomnias: Involuntary movements and behaviors during sleep. Talking in sleep, walking, night terrors, head banging, teeth grinding, bedwetting at night can be counted among the parasomnias.*
2. *Circadian rhythm disorders: Inconsistency of the individual's sleep pattern with other family members. Examples include sleeping less (insomnias) or sleeping too much (hypersomnias).*

3. What is night terror (night fright - pavor nocturnus)?

It is diagnosed by the presence of recurrent attacks, usually in the first one-third of sleep, with symptoms such as abrupt screaming in panic, marked fear, palpitation, rapid breathing, sweating. The person is unrelated to the environment and does not remember this attack when he wakes up in the morning. This attack usually lasts between 20 seconds and 5 minutes. It should not be expected that night terrors are necessarily related to a psychological reason, such as a horrific event or a tense environment. However, experiencing psychological trauma and being in a sensitive and anxious nature may increase the susceptibility. It is more common in those who have experienced separation situations. It occurs in about 3% of all children. It is more common around 5-7 years of age. The prognosis (i.e., afterward) is good. It does not cause a new disease. It can have a frightening appearance, which can cause a lot of anxiety to families. It is important to be careful not to be physically injured at the time. It may also be accompanied by an epileptic seizure (or like an epileptic seizure). Therefore, there is an absolute benefit in EEG evaluation and clinical examination. Once the condition is understood, appropriate treatment is given. Often, treatments are accompanied by drug treatments. Sleepwalking, on the other hand, is especially common at the age of 5-7 years. From the age of nine, its frequency decreases considerably. It is seen at least once in 30% of children. It is thought to be due to genetics.

In the first axis; problems (perturbation), disruptions (disturbance), or disorder (disorder) level,

- a. Nocturnal waking protodysonmia*
- b. falling asleep protodysonmia,*
- c. Sleep disturbance protodysonmia.*

On the second axis, associated with parent-child interaction styles

- a. Balanced / synchronized,*
- b. Overly intrusive/ controlling*
- c. Insufficiently relevant/ distant*
- D. Inconsistent/unpredictable.*

On the third axis; baby-related factors

- a. Regarding temperament,*
- b. Regarding the level of development,*
- c. It is about medical illness.*

On the fourth axis; environmental

- a. Stress related to family/marriage,*

- b. *parental stress,*
- c. *Psychopathology in the family,*
- D. *Trauma/domestic violence in the family.*

4. Autism – Sensory Integration – Sleep Relation

New research shows that young children with autism begin to have high sensory perception and sleep problems (especially around age 7). If there is noise in the environment, if light touches disturb you, if there is too much light and / or noise in the environment, it will be difficult to fall asleep.

In 12 academic centers providing medical care to children with autism in the USA and Canada, a study was conducted on sleep problems by evaluating autism assessment, intelligence test, frequency of sleep problems, sensory profiles and sensory sensitivities in 437 children between the ages of 2-10.

Sleep problems are not related to the child's age, gender, IQ, but are related to the socioeconomic level of the parent, and low-income families' bedtime routine, separate room, quiet environment, etc. It has been determined that sleep problems occur because they cannot create situations.

In autistic children with sleep problems due to sensory sensitivity, inattention and/or hyperactivity are observed later on, and there are also effects such as headaches and digestive disorders. The link between Sleep Problems and anxiety is common in children with autism. When they don't get enough sleep, they become more anxious, and more worrying makes it harder to sleep.

Experts recommend behavioral therapy for children with autism who have sleep problems and underline the importance of informing parents to manage their children's sleep problems.

Insufficient sleep can affect people's daily lives in a very negative way, and it can also lead to various health problems. Compared to children with normal development, sleep problems are more common in children with developmental disabilities such as autism spectrum disorder and intellectual disability. This situation not only negatively affects the daily activities of individuals with sleep problems, but also negatively affects other family members responsible for their care and increases their stress levels. For this reason, it is important to perform appropriate interventions for the elimination of sleep problems. Although there are various studies in the international literature on the study of sleep problems in children with developmental disabilities and the effectiveness of behavioral intervention methods, there are no behavioral intervention studies aimed at solving sleep problems, especially in the field of special education, in our country.

5. Sleep Scales

The gold standard for the diagnosis of sleep disorders is polysomnography. (“Relationship between perceived sleep and polysomnography in older adult ...”) Polysomnography is the simultaneous and continuous recording of many physiological parameters, especially neuro-physiological, cardiac, respiratory, during sleep, usually during the night. With this method, sleep stages and many physiological parameters are monitored in detail and information is provided about the functions of various organ systems and their interactions during sleep and wakefulness. Considering the dwindling number of sleep laboratories and centers where assessments of sleep

disorders are made in our country, it is thought that other measurement tools are needed. For this reason, it is recommended to perform an initial evaluation with sleep scales in terms of their easy applicability before proceeding to further examinations such as polysomnography in the evaluation of sleep problems.

One of these scales is the Pediatric Sleep Questionnaire developed by Ronald Chervin. There are two versions of the scale, seventy-two questions long and twenty-two questions short. While the short form is mostly associated with sleep-related respiratory problems, the comprehensive form can evaluate more sleep problems. Sleep Scale in Children; It consists of three parts: (A) behaviors at night and bedtime, (B) behaviors during the day, and (C) questions about attention deficit and hyperactivity. your scale: It has four subscales: behavioral problems, snoring, breathing problems and other problems. The breathing problems subscale shows 81% sensitivity and 87% specificity when compared to polysomnography, which is known as the gold standard in the diagnosis of obstructive sleep apnea syndrome.

Putting sleep into a certain order is a process that begins with birth. Sleep is one of the basic and indispensable daily life activities that affect the quality of life and health of individuals and is a concept with physiological, psychological, and social dimensions. (“Clinical Trial on Oncology Problem: exercise - Clinical Trials Registry ...”) Healthy sleep-in children are of critical importance for normal child development, general health of the child, school learning, emotional state, regulation of behavior, and stability of child's mood. Especially in children aged 0-3, behavioral problems arise in later ages due to night wakings and sleep problems. Therefore, it is important to define the sleep problem in children together with its cause. To define the cause of sleep problems in children, it is necessary to know the ecology of sleep. In putting the baby to sleep; Environmental factors such as parental behaviors, timing, environment, and decors form the sleep ecology. Sleeping behaviors of parents such as baby/child in bed/cradle, feeding, breastfeeding, cuddling, swinging, after bath, listening to tales alone or with another person in bed, watching television, while feeding, nursing, cuddling, and watching television are effective in their falling asleep. It is seen that it is possible to reduce the baby's sleep problems with the proper regulation of sleep ecology.

It is not correct to talk about a certain age for sleep training; however, considering that the habits of babies become ossified as they grow, it would be beneficial for families with sleep problems to solve these problems in the preliminary period. Many babies, by the time they are 4 months old, begin to sleep well; During this period, babies sleep longer during the day and strengthen their nighttime sleep. Therefore, as the age for starting sleep training, we can say that from the 5th month, unless preterm birth is out of the question. However, if parents can teach their babies the right sleep habits from the birth of their babies, they will be able to create a healthy sleep pattern without the need for sleep training.

Sleep is as important as nutrition in infant and child development. Especially in the 0-3 age period, 80% of brain development is achieved and most of this development takes place during sleep. At the same time, the hormone melatonin secreted during sleep; It strengthens the immune system and allows the pituitary gland to secrete more growth hormone. For this reason, babies are said to be “sleep and grow up”. A well-sleeping baby is also well-fed and, accordingly, has a healthy growth process.

All babies and children aged 0-5 should go to sleep at the latest between 20:00 and 21:00, while the morning departure time should be 8:00 at the latest. Your baby/child needs the growth

hormones secreted during these hours. A baby who goes to bed at 22:00 will not be able to benefit from the beneficial hormones secreted during sleep between 20:00 and 21:00. Likewise, a baby who wakes up late in the morning will be sleeping when the hormone secretion stops, and because his daily routine will shift forward, the evening bedtime will be delayed again. Correctly arranging bedtime and wake-up times is the most important step for a healthy, quality and productive sleep.

It is very important to put babies to bed at the right time so that they can fall asleep easily. The time that babies can stay awake varies according to the month. For example; While a newborn baby can stay awake for 40-60 minutes, a 6-month-old baby can stay awake for about 2 – 2.5 hours. Babies give some sleep signals such as yawning, ear tugging, eye rubbing when they are sleepy, which are unique to each baby. By paying attention to these signs and the times that should stay awake, you can observe that the baby can fall asleep much more easily and sleep more efficiently.

By applying routines before both daytime and evening naps, you should signal your baby that it's time to sleep and prepare him for sleep. The purpose of sleep routines; It is to take your baby away from daily activities, to calm him down and to give the message that it is time to sleep. An example routine might look like this: you can take your baby in your arms saying it's time to sleep, take your baby to his room singing a lullaby, turn on the music, close the curtains or blinds, and finally kiss him and leave him to bed. Thanks to sleep routines, you can observe that your baby calms down more easily, becomes more comfortable and falls asleep more easily. The most important point of sleep routines; It is to be applied absolutely and in the same order before each sleep.

For an ideal sleep environment, the room temperature should be around 20-21 degrees, babies sleep more comfortably in a cool environment. Your baby's bed should not contain anything (pillows, blankets, duvets, etc.) other than his sleeping companion. We recommend that there be no mosquito nets around the bed, no mobiles and similar stimulants on it.

We recommend the use of a sleeping bag in cold weather, as using a quilt or cover during sleep can be dangerous for babies. Using a sleeping bag according to the temperature of the room and your baby will be comfortable will increase the quality of sleep.

During daytime naps, you should darken your baby's room at bedtime so that he or she can fall asleep easily. Not using any light during night sleep will be beneficial for the full secretion of the hormone melatonin. Apart from sleeping, the room should be bright.

A sleep mate is a toy or object that will make it easier for your baby to sleep on their own and make them feel more secure. It will be beneficial not to remove the sleeping companion from the bed at all, but only to use it during sleep. Do not expect your baby to get used to the sleeping companion that you have given him, even if he is not interested for a while, you should continue to give it. If the object you choose as a sleeping companion is a toy, a small, soft and detachable nose, eye, button, etc. We recommend that you be careful not to. Babies can wake up when their sleep cycle is complete, just like adults. What we have to do at this point is to wait a bit and give him the opportunity to go back to sleep.

6. Factors That May Cause Sleeping Problems in Children

The temperament of the child is the communication between mother, father and child, nutrition, illness, physical conditions and bedtimes. The minutes you share with your child before they fall

asleep will be among the good memories that you will always remember with a smile with your children years later. Difficulty falling asleep or not being able to sleep soundly are observed not only in babies, but also sometimes in preschool or primary school children. Problems mostly arise when the child has to sleep alone or cannot free himself from the effects of the events he experiences during the day.

Nightmares are among the most common sleep disorders in children. While this situation is more common between 3-5 years of age, it can occur in all age groups. Nightmares may occur more frequently during stressful and anxious periods. Sleep terror, on the other hand, is when the child opens his eyes in fear, crying and shouting two or three hours after he goes to sleep, in fact he is in a heavy sleep. However, because the eyes are open in sleep terror, parents think they are awake. If the child is not awakened at this time and is put to bed again, he will not remember this situation in the morning. Narcolepsy: The person suddenly falls asleep while talking or eating, this can sometimes be accompanied by falling to the ground while standing. The frequency of these daytime sleep attacks negatively affects the quality of daily life of children. If it falls suddenly, it may hit the head and cause serious injury to the child.

The incidence of sleep disorders in children is high because sleep-wake regulation interacts with biological maturation and developmental factors. Studies reveal that about a quarter of children have trouble sleeping. It has been determined that sleep problems in children are in the form of difficulty falling asleep, waking up frequently at night, nightmares, bedwetting, nightmare disorder, talking in sleep, and teeth grinding. The rate of childhood insomnia disorder was found to be 1-6% in the general pediatric population. Addition of resistance to bedtime and problems with waking up during the night, the prevalence of sleep-related behavioral problems is 25-50% in preschool children.

There are differences between children in terms of sleep habits. Children between the ages of 1.5 and 2 need sleep at night, and at first, they are limited to afternoon sleep, which is a little longer. In the age of stubbornness, which usually starts in the 2nd or 3rd years, a period of patience begins for the parents. It is night and the child has to sleep. A 3-year-old child needs to sleep 11-12 hours a day, and the afternoon nap should not last more than 2 hours.

Television, portable technological electronic devices, nicotine, caffeine, internet are important environmental factors that affect the school child's sleep time. Media products consisting of technological electronic devices are important elements that make life easier. Today, it is accepted that electronic media has a negative effect on the sleep of children and adolescents. The technology age we live in makes our lives easier, but one of the most important problems it brings is technology addiction. A growing variety of media products and portable electronic devices (TEC) pose potential risks for children as well as adults. Although portable computers, smart mobile phones and tablets, which adults are busy with for long hours, seem to be indispensable necessities of our age, they create many harmful effects not only for adults but also for children with the addiction they create. Technological addiction is mentioned when it becomes an integral part of the daily life of children who spend more and more time with these media products, which have strong addictive potential effects .

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

The child should first be put to bed with a small ceremony. This ceremony should always be the same. A lullaby for small children that you can hum in a low voice or a toy clock that will start ringing when it's time to sleep is suitable for this purpose. While the calm and peaceful state of the parents has a positive effect on the child; restless and anxious states also affect the child immediately. For this reason, checking frequently and seeing if he is sleeping can have a negative effect on the child. It is important to stay away from exaggerated checks.

Some children relax after taking a bath and fall asleep comfortably, while others become active after bathing. Observe if your child calms down after a bath with warm water. Patting and patting the child can be comforting. If you see relief in your child after this application, you can apply this method regularly in the evening before going to bed. What your child is used to also plays an important role in his sleep. Sometimes when the things the child needs are out of the ordinary, your child may feel uneasy because of this. If you want to prepare for sleep in a new room, make sure to have familiar and favorite items ready in this room.

A calming massage is also effective for falling asleep. Melissa or Chamomile oil is effective as a massage oil. The sleep chart is also an effective method. During a week, regularly note when you take your child to bed, when he wakes up at night or in the morning, how long he sleeps, and how long he stays awake. In the sleep chart; The hours he slept, the time he was sleepless and the reasons should be included.

If you notice that your child is sleeping more than necessary during the day, you can try to wake him up for a while. In this case, you can caress or sing to your child. When it's time to sleep, it's important to make him feel it and go to his room together. It is important to talk to your child in a low voice and as little as possible during this process. If your child sleeps next to you and wakes up at night and finds himself in a different place, he may have trouble sleeping again. It will be a good method to ensure that your child continues to sleep in his own bed, and if he cannot sleep, you stay with him. Unusual things can also make children uncomfortable. If your child is having difficulty falling asleep in a way you have never seen before, or if he/she wakes up frequently during the night, you should investigate whether a change in the environment is causing this condition. An element that will help your child fall asleep is your patience with your child, your attitude to care about him and his problems, and your serious attitude that will support his self-confidence.

Color selection is very important in the selection of your child's bed linen. Colors that make people nervous should not be used in bedding. For example; yellow, red, orange these are worrying colors. Young children love bedding with flowers, toys and cute animals. An environment filled with items of calming colors is an ideal setting for sleep. The temperature and humidity of the room are also extremely important for a comfortable sleep. At bedtime, the temperature of the room should not rise above 18 degrees. It is necessary to leave the door of the room slightly ajar so that fresh air can enter the room continuously.

Eating large amounts of food before going to sleep also causes a major sleep problem. It is ideal to eat 2 hours before going to bed. Going to the toilet for the last time just before going to bed is also a precaution that will prevent your child from getting up after a while.

Make sure your child gets up from the screen before going to bed. There should be at least 1 hour between watching a movie and going to bed. You can talk to your child about what he has learned. You can explain to him the incomprehensible points, you can appease him by saying that the elements that seem threatening to him are just for the movie. It is also very important to make

preparations for going to bed . For example; going to the toilet, brushing teeth, bathing, putting on pajamas and saying good night to family members. Starting to tidy the room together can also be taken as a sign that the games are over. Bedtime is not open to discussion, but your child can use his own authority during the choice of pajamas or the toy that will be his sleep partner. In children with fear problems, a doorway where light can filter into the room or a night lamp that does not require much energy can help sleep. It should be treated in a way that will make you feel that the day is over and that you have to finish all your activities for now. This speech should be made without going into the details of the events. Making plans for the next day is also an effective method. For example; going to the park, visiting friends, etc. If you help him to visualize these in his mind, your child can fall asleep more easily with joy because of all this.

Drinking a glass of warm milk before going to bed at night is also a method that facilitates the transition to consciousness and sleep since ancient times. The L-tryptophan substance in milk makes people sleepy. Watching the stars shining in the sky at night gives peace of mind. By creating such an environment in your child's room, you can buy the moon grandfather and star figures in stationery.

Sleep patterns can also be achieved with the sleep breathing system. First, he should pay attention to how calm and regular you are breathing. Then he should close his eyes and focus on his own breathing. With this calming effect comes sleep. When it's time to go to bed, you can play a stretching game with your child.

When you realize that your child is afraid, you can walk around with him to check. You can show your child that there is nothing strange by lighting up every corner. Children who sleep alone in their rooms need a sleeping companion. Your child can tell him all his worries and protect him from everything he fears. If you make a beautiful fabric mosquito net decorated with stars on the bed in rooms with high ceilings, your child can transition to a more comfortable and happy sleep.

The child should lie in bed relaxed at the end of the day, breathe regularly, and focus his attention on his body. He should also say good night to his body. It would be very appropriate to tell a fairy tale as a sleep story, but the stories you will invent yourself will give just as good results. You can tell a story about an event that your child has experienced during the day, or you can have the story take place in a place where he or she knows him. You can also put their toys to sleep with a story. If a bad dream disturbed your child, encourage him to paint what he saw in his dream. When the picture is finished, ask it to describe what is on the page. Your child can continue to shape this pleasant dream in his head with the help of a picture. It has a sleep-inducing effect in the famous sheep counting game. Sheep, cats or butterflies can be imagined in this game. The child should always sleep in his own bed. In school-age children, social obligations and responsibilities may cause irregular sleep or sleepless nights for some children. The child should not make his bed a playground during the day, it is important to have a clean and tidy bed.

Encourage your child to talk about his school, teacher, friends. You can also join this conversation, you can tell your own school memories in a positive language. The child can write all the problems that bother him in his notebook. Although the problem is not solved as it is written, it will at least disturb your child less for a certain period of time. With self-relaxation exercises, the child can draw imaginary pictures that evoke relaxation, heaviness and warming in the mind. He should relax and be patient. Even concentrating on the exercises has a calming effect on its own. The child should close his eyes and lie on his back in a relaxed state. Finding a roommate for the child is

also an effective method. Fragrances of geranium, chamomile, lemon balm, sandalwood and ylang-ylang create a relaxing effect before sleep.

Caffeinated beverages should also be avoided. Green tea really has a stimulating effect. Black tea can also cause sleep problems if brewed for more than three minutes. One of the causes of sleep problems can be iron deficiency. Legumes such as peas and beans are reliable sources of iron. The iron ratio in fish and meat is also well absorbed by the body. If your child is constantly turning in bed and cannot sleep, you can take an evening stroll with him.

It is especially important to develop a healthy sleep pattern from the newborn period, which also affects the attention, success, social development, and physical abilities of children in later ages, and to establish a healthy sleep pattern.

8. Resources

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